

Searcher Heterogeneity in Collaborative Information Seeking within the Context of Students Work Tasks

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Abstract

This paper shows an overview over a doctoral thesis project which focuses on Collaborative Information Seeking (CIS) with a core interest in searcher heterogeneity. A special field of interest is the way how different personalities interact in a collaborative search scenario and if heterogeneous groups perform better or worse than homogenous groups. The goal is to provide a description of group performance in CIS, to get suggestions for the design of collaborative search tools and to create a model of CIS integrating search heterogeneity.

Keywords: Collaborative Information Seeking, Group Performance, Personality

1 Motivation and background

Collaborative Information Seeking (CIS) is a quite new field in the area of Information Seeking research. Despite the fact that researchers claim collaboration is a helpful method for solving complex problems, CIS is still under-

In: F. Pehar/C. Schlögl/C. Wolff (Eds.). Re:inventing Information Science in the Networked Society. Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Information Science (ISI 2015), Zadar, Croatia, 19th–21st May 2015. Glückstadt: Verlag Werner Hülsbusch, pp. 494–500.

studied (Shah 2012). Knowledge is collectively created in this context and therefore different from knowledge a single actor would create (Kölle et al. 2006). CIS is an everyday task e.g. in the area of teaching and learning. Hyldegard, for instance, studied the applicability of Kuhlthau's information search process (Kuhlthau 1991) in the context of a group-based educational setting (Hyldegard 2006). CIS performance depends on different aspects which are not exhaustively explored. Research on team performance in working scenarios, however, shows that one aspect influencing collaboration is personality (Belbin 1981). Heinström carried out a Ph.D. thesis showing the influence of personality on individual Information Seeking (Heinström 2002).

2 Research questions

The overall aim of the doctoral thesis project is to highlight collaborative search performance of teams with regard to the different personalities of the team members. The results should help deviating search strategies and support measures for the design of CIS-tools and could further support the development of a model which implements searcher heterogeneity with regards to search roles. In general, this research project should help to get and provide a deeper understanding on how people search collaboratively. The research questions which frame this project are as follows:

RQ1: How do teams organize collaborative search?

- a) Which search strategies are carried out?
- b) Which resources are used?
- c) What kind of process can be examined?
- d) How do people discuss and compare search results?

RQ2: Is it possible to examine certain types of behaviors in CIS which are connected to the personality of the searchers?

- a) Are their prototypical search-roles being adopted during CIS?
- b) If there are such roles how do they shape their search?
- c) In which ways interact different personalities during CIS?

RQ3: Which system-based provisions can support collaborative search according to the research results?

- a) Which tools or applications can support collaborative search?

- b) Which tools or applications are likely to be accepted by the searchers, which ones run the risk of being rejected?

RQ4: Do the findings lead to a new model of CIS?

- a) Is it possible to integrate user-heterogeneity in this model?
- b) Is it possible to expand existing models and integrate CIS-structures?

3 Methodology

The main experiment is carried out between October 2014 and February 2015 at the University of Hildesheim. Because of the complexity of the object of research, the methodology needs to cover three different parameters: information seeking, team performance and personality. To cover many aspects of collaborative behavior and to gain a deeper understanding of the processes involved, a qualitative research design was developed which includes collection of search data, diary studies, guided group interviews and questionnaires. The test participants are master students from the field of international information management (IIM) participating in a course on information ethics. The target group was chosen because of the following reasons: IIM-students often have to work in projects involving collaborative search activities. Most of the students do not live in Hildesheim but commute between the University and Hannover or the nearby area. That again leads to distributed work where the support of a tool such as SearchTeam is reasonable.

To successfully complete the course on information ethics the students are supposed to give a 60 min presentation and to hand in a written report. For the purpose of the experiment, they are allowed to work in teams up to three members.

To be able to collect search data and get feedback on the acceptance of CIS-tools, the participants are asked to use SearchTeam¹ to handle the tasks. The groupware SearchTeam provides support for CIS and gives users the possibility to save, manage and share information. In addition it provides a chat which can be used for synchronous communication. Taken aside the

¹ Publicly available from <http://searchteam.com/>

aspects of being cost free and publicly available, the tool turned out to be very useful for conducting this study.

The data collected via SearchTeam includes chat data, emails and search results, e.g. snippets, websites and articles. The students are asked to write search diaries evaluating each search session. The aim of the diary study is to collect data on the search process from individual perspectives.

After the search, the students are asked to participate in a guided group interview, with a focus on actual done collaborative search. Each group will be asked on how they experienced the search in teamwork, what they liked or disliked and what they think are the main differences between collaborative and individual search. An additional set of questions will focus on the experiences the participants made while using the search tool. In the following, the students are asked to fill out a questionnaire which focuses mainly on collecting information to determine the data linked to the participant's personality. Belbin's team role questionnaire (Belbin 1981) turned out to be very useful for gaining personality data in a series of pretests. With the questionnaire it is further possible to get additional data which can help to gain a short overview over the information search behavior of the participants and their general attitude towards teamwork.

4 Planned analysis

As described in section 3, the planned methodology is extensive and accordingly, the collected data will be too. For the main study it is planned to have eight to ten teams of two to three members. The search diaries, the data generated by using SearchTeam and the data from the group interviews, as well as a set of questionnaires from each team will be collected and studied. The analysis of the questionnaire is mostly quantitative and should provide data to figure out the team role(s) each participant usually takes in team work scenarios, the information search behavior and the attitude towards team work. The analysis of the search diary will be qualitative and should help to get information on how each individual experienced the collaborative search process. Since the data from the questionnaire and the search diaries is based on self-report, the information collected via SearchTeam during the search process has the potential of being a valuable source of objective data. The

analysis of the system data will be qualitative and should also highlight the actual search-performance, i.e. which information sources are used or how the team communicates during the search process. The focus on the qualitative analysis of the guided group interviews lies on the collaborative search and the experiences the participants made as a team. Furthermore, this data should highlight the experiences the teams by using this tool.

5 Progress made so far and first results

In 2012 a preliminary experiment was carried out (Kußmann et al. 2013). It was shown that quantitative experiments for analyzing the effects of personality factors are hard to design, since so many parameters are involved.

In June and July 2014 a pretest was carried out with 101 participants, all information science students in their first year of study. The participants were asked to complete a task in groups of three to four people which was part of a recitation in the area of information management. Because of the number of participants, only eight groups were asked to attend the guided group interviews. The pretest led to some changes in the main experiment and provided first results in respect to the research questions:

The analysis of RQ1 shows that all examined teams split the complex task up into smaller subtasks. After the results got compiled, they were discussed by the whole group again. Furthermore, the teams preferred to work online and in distributed environments rather than face-to-face. Preliminary results on RQ2 show that the teams which consist of various team roles usually get better and more diverse search results. In addition it seems to be necessary to have one person who takes the role of the team leader to be able to organize the team work. That seems to be more relevant in bigger teams than in smaller ones. First findings on RQ3 led to the assumption that the possibility of having a single tool for collecting and commenting on search results, may turn out to be very useful for CIS. The search function in the test tool was seldomly used and the participants usually preferred to use Google for their search, stating that here, the results are “more and better” compared to SearchTeam. The main problem is, as stated by the participants, the missing alert function in SearchTeam: they always had to log in to see if their team members added results which led to a higher effort and a discontinuous workflow.

In addition, the participation in the doctoral consortium at the IiiX'14 (Elbeshausen et al. 2014) provided a lot of helpful input, which helped to reconsider and improve the used research questions and methods.

6 Future plans

The next planned step is the analysis and interpretation of data from the main experiment. The results of the experiment should then be compared to existing systems and models in (C)IS in order to judge them in regards to their usefulness for modeling collaborative information search. In the end, we plan to give recommendations for the design of CIS tools and if necessary, a new model for CIS. Both should be in respect to user heterogeneity, i.e. the different team roles of team members in CIS.

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